

ANALYSIS OF SOLVING IRRATIONAL EQUATIONS USING THE GEOGEBRA SOFTWARE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17452728>

Annotation: This article examines the basic concepts of the topic “*Irrational Equations*”, which is a part of the section “*Irrational Equations and Inequalities*” in mathematics. It analyzes several examples related to the introduction of this topic, as well as their examination using the GeoGebra software. The purpose of this analysis is to explain, through examples and diagrams, the meaning and importance of the fundamental concepts that students of general secondary education should pay attention to when solving irrational equations.

Keywords: irrational numbers, irrational equations, domain of definition, modern methods.

Introduction

Today, alongside the growing demand for the development of the school mathematics curriculum, one of the most pressing issues faced by teachers in general secondary education is how to organize mathematics lessons in a high-quality and effective manner that prevents students from losing interest in the subject [4,5,6].

At this point, it is worth mentioning Abu Rayhon Beruni’s views on the methods and approaches to acquiring scientific knowledge. According to him, in the process of teaching students, attention should be paid to the following:

- Do not bore the learner.
- Avoid constantly teaching the same concepts or subjects.

Taking these ideas into account, this article analyzes the topic “Simple Irrational Equations and Their Systems” from the school mathematics course for 10th-grade students. It discusses both the conveniences and the challenges that arise in the process of teaching this topic.

Examples related to finding the domain of definition in order to determine whether a solution exists or not:

Example 1:

$$\sqrt{2x-3} + \sqrt{1-x} = 5$$

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Let the equation be given. Before finding the solution to this equation, we first determine its domain of definition.

$$\begin{cases} 2x-3 \geq 0 \\ 1-x \geq 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow x \geq 1.5, x \leq 1$$

From the diagram above and the determined domain of definition, it is evident that there is no region in which this equation has a solution. Now, let us consider this equation as the equality of two functions and check, using the GeoGebra software, whether these functions intersect. To do this, we first rewrite the equation as follows:

$$\sqrt{2x-3} = 5 - \sqrt{1-x}$$

We rewrite it in the following form, $y = \sqrt{2x-3}$, $y = 5 - \sqrt{1-x}$ and consider them as functions, then plot their graphs using the GeoGebra software.

Indeed, as can be seen from the graphs, these two functions do not intersect, and therefore the solution of this equation is the empty set.

$\sqrt{f(x)} = g(x)$ Equations of the following form and examples related to their solutions:

Example 7: $2\sqrt{x+5} = x+2$

Solution: To find the solution of this equation, we first determine its domain of definition.

$$\begin{cases} x+2 \geq 0 \\ x+5 \geq 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x \geq -2 \\ x \geq -5 \end{cases}$$

Now, we square both sides of the equation.

$$2\sqrt{x+5} = x + 2$$

$$4x + 20 = x^2 + 4x + 4$$

$$x^2 = 16$$

$$x_{1,2} = \pm 4$$

According to the domain of definition, the solution of the equation is equal to $x = \dots$ (based on the determined value).

Now, to solve this equation as well, we consider it as the equality of two functions, just as we did above, and analyze their graphs using the GeoGebra software.

$$\begin{cases} y = 2\sqrt{x+5} \\ y = x + 2 \end{cases}$$

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